

VR FOR EDUCATION

IN SCHOOLS

FIRST STEPS IN VR

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Introduction

The rapid development of technology in recent decades has affected to a very significant extent every aspect of human activity. As was completely expected, the field of education has also received enormous effects and changes since the entry of modern technological achievements. It is now clear that the traditional teacher-centered way of teaching in the classroom is under intense questioning, as are the principles it advocates.

Modern pedagogy is undoubtedly more oriented towards a more **student-centered** teaching system, which responds to the student's individual needs in the process of his learning development, but also to the provisions of the modern era.

The entry and integration of information and communication technologies in education was a difficult process, and it took several years for the educational world to successfully assimilate it. Today, the use of computer systems and their functions is considered an integral and necessary part of educational activity, to such an extent that their absence often makes teaching impossible. In this way, we could say that it is now IT and education are interrelated concepts.

In the last decade, the rapid development of technology has yielded new ways to develop learning applications. Virtual reality as an educational medium is becoming increasingly accessible to students and

professionals. It is a new medium that offers unique advantages.

The **virtual reality (VR)** environment is now considered one of the most modern tools that can be used in education, and there is general recognition of the possibilities and support it gives to the educational process. It has found scope in most subjects and levels of education, with positive results. In general, it helps provide high-quality learning experiences to a broad population of students who may not be physically present in the field.

The **European Union** is very keen to fund programs implementing Virtual Reality applications in schools. Through the Erasmus+ program, pilot studies about the use of VR for learners with special learning needs are being carried out and exhibit positive results. Through the interaction with virtual environments those individuals can socialize, communicate, and use their senses to experience the world as they have never done before. Thus, they can feel that they belong to a group and that they can offer help to society. In addition, in January 2021, the world's first educational virtual reality theme park was opened. In this park learners can tour, work in groups, travel to another period, test constructions. Teachers, on the other hand, can participate, research, and receive feedback on the knowledge gained.

Worth to mention the VR@School which makes intensive use of ICT in teaching and learning activities resulting in a large percentage (more than 50%) of students who become familiar with digital online applications.

In conclusion, we must underline the policy of the European Union to evolve and develop technological and industrial tools, offered by the Internet, in favor of education. In the EU Report about Technological Trends and Policies it is recognized how much the field of education will change in the near future with the integration of Artificial Intelligence, Augmented and Virtual Reality, BigData, Blockchain, Nanoelectronics, Robotics and Security.

With this e-book, we would like to share all these experiences and the products of our fruitful collaboration. This manual is one of the specific results. In this handbook, they find the framework conditions and descriptions of situations in the respective partner countries. You'll also find ready-made courses and training modules that are tested and reflect the parties and participants.

This project has been carried out by three institutions from different countries: from Greece, 1er EPAL of Piraeus; from Lithuania, the NGO Motyvaciniai projektai; and from Spain, IES Diego Velázquez.

1er EPAL of Piraeus stands out for providing training in various professional fields, equipped with specialized laboratories and actively collaborating with local businesses. Recognized for its achievements in theater and participation in European programs like Erasmus+, the school aims to strengthen its digital dimension and enhance social inclusion. With 60 teachers and around 450 students, it focuses on addressing those with economic and social challenges, implementing information technology-based methodologies to improve academic performance and equality of opportunities.

Motyvaciniai Projektai (Mpro) is a non-governmental organization (NGO) based in Lithuania, actively engaged in the field of educational technology (EdTech), with a specific emphasis on virtual reality (VR) and web3 technologies. Driven by a mission to propel education through cutting-edge information and communication technologies, Mpro boasts extensive expertise in EdTech advancements, web3 innovations, and entrepreneurial proficiency.

IES Diego Velázquez is a Trilingual school (Spanish, English and French) located in the suburban town of Torrelodones, on the outskirts of Madrid. With approximately 1200 students and 86 teachers, the institution is committed to sharing its expertise and learning from other professionals, promoting cooperation among schools from various countries and cultures.

Good Practices in VR Education: Insights from Greece

Virtual Reality is a technology used to produce a computer-generated virtual 3D environment that we can interact it as it was "real". The illusion of "real" is created because our senses are fed with fabricated information by specialized hardware devices (e.g., virtual reality glasses) forcing our brain to form a perspective of a reality that does not exist.

VR is a promising tool that can be used in our school to form modern educational practices. It can provide students with a cooperative and exploratory learning and pedagogical support having as a goal the best learning outcome. Moreover, it offers a safe environment regarding situations that are impossible, too complicated or even dangerous to be recreated in the real world. It allows students to experience and understand unfamiliar situations that drive behavioral issues. For example, students can learn speaking in low voice and not making noise next to an autistic person by virtually living their life and dealing with their everyday problems.

Greece situation

The Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs of Greece presented the 5+1 main axes of the government's work in the field of Education, highlighting the effort to comprehensively upgrade the country's education system and ensuring more and better quality education for our young people.

In Greece, nowadays, we can see a growing interest in introducing new technologies, especially virtual reality, in educational processes. One of these axes is the improvement of educational infrastructure and equipment. It is stated that 90,000 laptops/tablets will be provided for schools. Robotics equipment, interactive whiteboards, and faster internet will be ensured in all schools. Special advanced technological equipment for students with special educational needs and disabilities, and virtual reality laboratories will be established in 100

schools of the country. Innovation Centers, one in each region, and modern technological equipment will be given to all the Laboratory Centers of the Vocational Education and Training structures. For those schools that want to introduce virtual reality in their classrooms, funding typically comes from European programs, especially the Erasmus+ program.

Many universities organize virtual reality workshops and create synergies and partnerships emphasizing in training programs on game development and animation. Lectures and workshops on subjects attracting young people such as smart cities, bitcoins, digital marketing, gaming etc. is now given throughout the country.

Moreover, several companies develop training programs and offer services to assist the use of virtual reality in schools.

A.P.Th. University, Regional Directorate of Education, NOISIS, University of Athens, Application of Virtual Reality in schools by NOISIS

A VR world have been developed for teaching Geography. It creates a virtual flight over Greece. The flight includes 360-degree films taken in selected areas of Greece such as the Vikos Gorge, the Polyphytos Lake, Mount Olympus, etc. and will be observed by the students with the help of special glasses for 3D – 360° observations.

Private Companies Learning foreign languages

With the Unimersiv app and the Oculus Rift headset, students can "meet" virtually with people from any country in the world and chat with them. This particular interactive experience is called the "Language Room" and users can improve their social skills and learn about different cultures. Unimersiv allows students to practice their language skills in a real-life environment. The application is available for free on the Oculus Store.

BrainFirst: Non-profit Company

In 2019 a non-profit company named BrainFirst has been established to actively create and adapt VR technology to the educational needs of the country.

Its founder's stated: "During a scholarship at Apple's model academy we realized a significant gap between education and technology in Greek schools. As a result, we created BrainFirst [...] to bridge this gap through VR days in schools and knowledge centers."

BrainFirst's first VR game for Greek schools, is about recycling. It introduces students to a digital world where recycling is crucial for the sustainability of our country and/or planet.

Other Apps

Furthermore, it should be noted that due to the unfavorable economic conditions prevailing in Greece in recent years, introducing new technologies and specialized hardware devices into public schools of all stages is not so easy. Several private companies are developing and offering the appropriate equipment and programs for education and entertainment. Examples of such programs are:

- A tour of the 7 Wonders of Antiquity (VR Planet)
- An encounter with a larger whale (VR Planet)
- A dive into History to see the Acropolis (VR Planet)
- A visit to the International Space Station ISS (VR Planet)
- Personal, Social and Citizenship Education (ClassVR)
- Literacy and Language Arts (ClassVR)
- Drama, Theatre And Performing Arts (ClassVR)
- Travel and Tourism (ClassVR)

and many more...

However, virtual reality in schools is still in its early stages. Very few schools offer virtual reality experiences to their students, and even fewer have the appropriate infrastructure and tools for teaching.

University of Ioannina

University of Ioannina has developed 4 different applications.

LAKE Project

At the University of Ioannina, the LAKE Project was developed, which targets high school students and deals with the issue of eutrophication in lakes. In an environmental information center, after the user receives information about the phenomenon of eutrophication from various media (slides, comics), they enter 3 virtual environments where they explore the bottom of a lake and see the condition that prevails when there is different levels of pollution.

V-Laser

At the University of Ioannina, the V-LASER application was developed, which is aimed at undergraduate students and deals with the topic of laser physics. The user has the ability to explore the virtual components that make up a laser device, use them appropriately to assemble it, put it into operation, and study its operating conditions.

Laser Physics Lab

The University of Ioannina in collaboration with the University of Nottingham developed the Laser Physics Lab, which is aimed at high school students and undergraduate students and deals with the topic of basic physics of laser light. The application provides information on spontaneous and stimulated emission of radiation, radiation scattering, an illustration of the electric component of the electromagnetic field, and finally a holography arrangement that can be put into operation.

Plant Cell

At the University of Ioannina, Plant Cell was developed, which is aimed at high school students and deals with the topic of the structure of the plant cell and the process of photosynthesis. The application consists of two parts. In the first part, the user enters a virtual plant cell and explores its structure by navigating inside it. They see the structure of the organelles in space, enter inside them, and can observe the processes taking place inside them. In the second part, the user enters the interior of a chloroplast, finds the elements necessary for the process of photosynthesis, and is called upon to complete it on their own.

Good Practices in VR Education: Insights from Lithuania

The evolution of Virtual Reality (VR) technologies has transcended their initial applications in gaming and entertainment, finding newfound relevance across diverse sectors, notably in education.

Enhancing Learning Experiences

VR offers a more engaging and tangible learning experience for users of all age groups. Interactive educational methods provide motivating, interesting, and memorable learning experiences. These technologies allow the visualization of complex processes, contexts, and relationships, creating virtual environments that transcend physical classroom boundaries. The impact of immersive and playful environments opens up entirely new possibilities in education, often surpassing traditional methods.

Perspective for Lithuania

While Lithuania has been a pioneer in the development of computer games, Tautvydas Pipiras, the Projects Manager at the Lithuanian Innovation Center, emphasizes the need for the country to broaden its application of VR technologies. These technologies have transcended the confines of the gaming industry, permeating fields such as medicine, professional training, education, manufacturing, and engineering. To maintain competitiveness, Lithuania should embrace the growing opportunities presented by VR and allocate attention to the industrial gamification trend.

As the global landscape embraces the increasing use of VR technologies, Lithuania stands at the cusp of a technological revolution. The diverse applications of VR, from enhancing education to revolutionizing professional training, present an array of opportunities for the country's innovation sector.

Beyond Gaming: Exploring the Educational Potential of VR

Virtual reality is a technology used for entertainment purposes and that is why many users tend to look at VR as a console solely used for gaming and other similar activities. While the technology can be used for entertainment, it is important to highlight other areas in which it also can be used, especially - education. Good samples could be:

- Secrets of the Partisans - <https://www.magiccalf.lt/>

Partizanu Paslaptys (eng. Secrets of the Partisans) is a virtual experience, Partizanu Paslaptys (eng. Secrets of the Partisans) where kids can learn more about the history of Partisans, meet them and immerse themselves in their history. The author of the education stresses the importance of informal education, and this is a great example of a correct way of implementing virtual reality into the learning process. The experience allows the users to see first-hand what hardships did the partisans face, what dangerous missions they needed to pursue and talks about their views and values. It is important to highlight, that the pupils are more likely to engage in the learning process that allows them to participate in the session with the help of an innovative tool – virtual reality.

- Along the paths of Angels - <https://angelutakais.lt/>

It is important to talk about ways to make learning about our culture and art more interesting, because it's essential for boosting creativity and development of people's self-expression. That's why it is very welcomed, that in several cities in Lithuania including pupils and students can immerse themselves into an interactive movie called „Angely takais” (eng. Along the paths of Angels) about the cultural heritage of M. K. Čiurlionis. This movie allows user to connect with 60 paintings of this famous Lithuanian artist in 25 minutes of screen time.

- Zen Republic HQ – www.zenrepublic.space.

The COVID pandemic also introduced schools to new challenges, like remote classes that were a tough pill to swallow for many educators. Most of them struggled to keep the class engaged while being online, and therefore student engagement was way lower than in live classes. However, by experimenting with virtual reality, they can find a simple and interactive solution to ensure that pupils and students are actively engaged in lectures and their motivation remains high. There are a lot of virtual spaces, that can be used for remote work possibilities, one of which is a local project that is called Zen Republic HQ. It is a metaverse, that can be used for events, classes, conferences, and other educational purposes but also for having lots of fun! It is also worth mentioning that many educational events can take place in a virtual space, and seminars, conferences and similar events can not only make the participant more interested, but also offer great interactive solutions to make the person want to come back next time.

Conclusion

The utilization of VR in education presents both opportunities and challenges. While the technology holds the promise of revolutionizing the learning experience, issues such as content creation, safety, and the availability of VR devices must be addressed. As universities and institutions invest in VR laboratories and initiatives, they play a crucial role in shaping the future of education by harnessing the potential of immersive technologies.

Good Practices in VR Education: Insights from Spain

The goal of this report is to assess the current state of Virtual Reality (VR) implementation in secondary schools in the Madrid region within the context of the Project AIM. Although VR adoption among secondary teachers is not widespread, its potential for enhancing educational processes is significant.

Main finding / conclusions

VR is progressively gaining ground in education in Spain, particularly in Madrid. Funded projects, teacher training courses, and infrastructure investments indicate sustained growth in VR integration in classrooms, a trend expected to continue. Several private universities, such as IE University and U-Tad, offer degrees and courses on VR, contributing to a broader shift in higher education toward immersive technologies. Additionally, public universities like Complutense and Rey Juan Carlos University have introduced Master's programs in VR, reflecting a comprehensive approach.

Additionally, many health science degrees are incorporating VR into their practices, allowing students to experience medical scenarios in a safe and realistic way.

While private institutions like Obicex and Implika offer Professional Training courses in VR, the presence of such programs in public schools in the Community of Madrid is limited. However, IES La Arboleda stands out as the sole public center offering a specialized VET course in Video Game Development and Virtual Reality. Promoting VR integration in public education is crucial to ensuring equitable access to these opportunities.

A notable example of successful VR integration is the Curri Project, recognized as one of the most innovative projects in CaixaBank Dualiza and FPEmpresa call for FP center grants, exemplifies successful technology integration into Vocational Training centers. Specifically, students in the “Grado Medio Sistemas Microinformáticos y Redes” and “Grado Superior de Desarrollo de Aplicaciones” programs engage in VR application development using Unreal. This initiative not only introduces technology but actively involves students in the process, showcasing the positive impact of VR on educational experiences.

Proyecto Curri:

<https://www.youtube.com/@proyectorri>

For now, there is a lack of VR utilization in state-funded secondary schools, coupled with a shortage of official training in this technology. Nevertheless, a growing trend, particularly in vocational education, sees more institutions incorporating VR, especially for work simulations.

Technology has demonstrated its ability to provide new experiences and elevate education to the next level. Employing VR methods like "liquid learning" can lead to active, collaborative, applied, and personalized learning. VR plays a pivotal role in contemporary society by revolutionizing relationships between people and machines, bridging the gap between the real and digital worlds.

All in all, VR is increasingly being embraced in education in Spain, particularly in Madrid, as indicated by funded projects, teacher training courses, and infrastructure investments. This upward trajectory is expected to continue, with more schools adopting VR technology to offer immersive educational experiences.

Support and training

The Ministry of Education supports VR innovation through the "Educa en Digital" program, co-financing center projects. Some autonomous communities also encourage VR use with their digitalization plans. Various training courses, ranging from basic VR technology introductions to creating interactive educational content, have been developed to effectively train teachers in VR use.

Conclusion

VR is increasingly utilized in education in Spain, especially in Madrid, with ongoing growth indicated by funded projects, teacher training courses, and infrastructure investments. This upward trend is expected to continue, with more schools adopting VR technology to provide immersive educational experiences.

As VR and AR continue to advance, their presence in education is anticipated to intensify. Collaboration between educators and content creators will be crucial for designing high-quality, engaging, and accessible educational experiences that meet the needs of students in the digital era within the framework of Project AIM.

Recommendations

Highly recommending training courses for secondary teachers, along with public funding for VR devices in schools.

Limitations and impact

VR is gaining popularity in Spanish schools, especially since the COVID-19 pandemic, although classroom adoption remains limited. Challenges include ensuring pedagogical quality, integrating VR into the curriculum, and evidencing its real impact on learning.

Future trends in the use of VR in education

- Mass adoption at all educational levels due to cost reductions in VR devices.
- Development of high-quality immersive educational content.
- Utilizing VR for experiential learning and boosting soft skills.
- Personalization of learning through adapted VR content.
- Collaborative VR classrooms for interaction and collaboration in shared virtual environments.

VR Device Management

VR IN EDUCATION

Virtual reality or VR, the use of a computer modeling and simulation that enables a person to interact with an artificial three-dimensional (3D) visual or another sensory environment. The environment is perceived through a head mounted display (HMD) called a VR headset.

Glossary

Virtual reality (VR) - simulated immersive 3D environment;

Augmented reality (AR) - physical world is overlaid with a layer of digital content;

Mixed reality (MR) - virtual objects are integrated into the physical world;

Extended reality (XR) - computer generated environments that merge the physical and virtual worlds.

PwC VR soft-skills training study conclusion:

Institutions should consider a **multimodal approach** in the future, as VR can be ideal for practicing what you learn in a safe and dynamic way. When you combine classroom, e-learn, and v-learn together, you are helping provide your learners with an industry leading approach. This new modality will likely help transform this new age of training and education.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KCBwUySF4uk>

VR device could be used for:

1. Soft skill training;
2. Language improvement, public speaking, roleplay;
3. Virtual field trips;
4. Immersive history, arts, geography lessons;
5. Internships or remote work;
6. Mental health and fitness;
7. Research, scientific experimentations.

STEP BY STEP GUIDE FOR EDUCATORS

STEP 1: Headset

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XpJ2LvS35VE>

STEP 2: Controllers

STEP 3: Meta Quest Safety Instructions

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l63yL3xjONw>

STEP 4: Guardian

STEP 5: First steps

VR App 'First steps' is a short experience made for you to become acquainted with your controllers and showcase the power of Meta Quest.

STEP 6: Download apps

- Create your Meta account: [Meta Account Creation](#)
- Download the Meta Quest mobile app or access the Oculus app store through your PC or VR headset: [Oculus App Store](#)
- Browse the Meta Quest store and App Lab for free app subscriptions or to make purchases.

Meta Quest store

Purchasing an App

Also explore apps suitable for Arts & Design classes: [10 VR Apps for Artists](#)

STEP 7: Cast to your audience

- Open oculus.com/casting
- Tap the "Sharing" button on your VR headset.
- Tap the "Cast" button.
- Select "Computer".

Open oculus.com/casting

Tap "Sharing" button in your VR headset

Tap the "Cast" button.

Select "Computer"

After completing Step 1 to Step 7, you will be fully equipped to immerse yourself in the world of VR and share your experiences with your students.

Tips for VR device management

Before lesson

- 1. Check Device Readiness:**
 - Charge VR headsets for at least 2 hours.
 - Green LED: 100% charged, Orange: 10-100%, Red: below 10%.
 - Controllers' charge level can only be checked when the device is on.
- 2. Internet Connection:**
 - Ensure WiFi is connected; check the wireless icon.
- 3. Matching Headsets and Controllers:**
 - Confirm each headset matches its controllers, especially if stored together.
- 4. App Updates:**
 - Update apps when time allows for a consistent student experience.
- 5. Disinfectant and Spacers:**
 - Have enough disinfectant and spacers for cleaning after each use.
 - Ensure spacers for students with glasses.

Planing the lesson Area

- 1. Physical Space**
 - Allocate 1x1 meters for less movement or 3x3 meters for active experiences.
- 2. Light**
 - Ensure moderate lighting for optimal tracking; avoid extreme brightness or darkness.
- 3. Avoid Sunlight on Lenses**
 - Protect headsets from direct sunlight to prevent damage.

Preparing Students:

- 1. Assign Headsets**
 - Assign headsets to students based on prepared real-world spaces.
- 2. Spacer for Glasses**
 - Recommend adding a spacer for students wearing glasses.
- 3. Adjust Headset for Comfort**
 - Instruct students to adjust straps for comfort and clarity.
- 4. Lens Distance Adjustment**
 - Show how to adjust lens distance for individual comfort.
- 5. Recenter Position in VR**
 - Explain how to recenter if the virtual world seems distant.
- 6. Understand Main Buttons**
 - Briefly explain the functions of main buttons on controllers.
- 7. Wear Wrist Straps**
 - Emphasize wearing wrist straps for safety during VR activities.
- 8. Draw Guardian Area or Set "Standing Only" Mode**
 - Guide students based on available space to draw a guardian area or set the mode.

During lesson

- 1. Safety Check**
 - Ensure VR areas have enough buffer space.
 - Confirm all students wear wrist straps.
 - Verify properly fastened head straps.
- 2. Reposition if Needed:**
 - Instruct students to reset their position if drifted from the center.

After the VR Lesson:

- 1.** Turn off headsets completely to save battery. Long press the power button until the shutdown sound is heard.
- 2.** Clean headsets with non-alcoholic disinfectant.
- 3.** Ensure controllers are stored with their corresponding headsets.
- 4.** Use a storage box for organized storage.
- 5.** Provide multiple USB ports or extension cords for charging.
- 6.** Protect headsets from direct sunlight.
- 7.** Ensure safe charging to minimize fire hazards.
- 8.** Ensure wifi coverage for app installations and updates.

In summary, by following the steps provided in VR device management chapter, you can ensure your VR devices remain safe, functional, and durable, ultimately enhancing the learning experience for your students.

Tecno**l**ogy Solving problem

DESIGN & TECHNOLOGY Age 13-15

Learning Aims:

- Understand what virtual reality is and become familiar with some of its applications.
- Collaboratively explore real-world problems or needs.
- Work in teams to design innovative solutions.
- Develop prototypes in response to identified needs.
- Cultivate teamwork, critical thinking, and creativ problem-solving skills.
- Navigate the iterative process of conceptualizing, designing, and presenting prototypes.

Context

It's essential that students are equipped with the skills to address real-world challenges by harnessing the power of prototyping and collaborative design. Recognizing the importance of fostering creativity and problem-solving abilities, our curriculum emphasizes hands-on experiences using cutting-edge tools like Gravity Sketch, a virtual reality-based 3D modeling platform. Gravity Sketch emerges as a transformative tool, enabling students to sculpt and refine ideas in an immersive virtual reality environment.

Practical session

This teaching sequence takes place over a series of sessions (50-55 minutes/session). The initial introduction explores the theory behind VR and highlights practical examples, followed by a lesson familiarizing students with VR devices and practices in a virtual scenario. The third lesson introduces the specific methodology of Gravity Sketch, offering students the opportunity to create individual 3D projects (with training best practices from Gravity Sketch serving as references). The final lesson focuses on the evaluation and presentation of these projects, encouraging critical review and group collaboration. In summary, this teaching sequence aims not only to teach the fundamentals of VR but also to provide students with practical and creative skills in the application of this emerging technology.

Impact on learning

The ability to view and manipulate 3D designs in virtual reality, from the beginning to the end, adds a tactile dimension to the process of designing and making a real-world object. This hands-on experience can evoke a sense of excitement and engagement among students, especially when using virtual reality glasses.

This approach is particularly helpful for students who find 3D visualization difficult, offering a valuable opportunity to discuss how designs can be optimized and improved.

Lesson 1

Introduction to Virtual Reality (VR) and Its Applications -2 sessions

Objectives:

1. Knowledge and Understanding:

- Explain fundamental concepts of virtual reality by the end of the lesson.
- Demonstrate a solid understanding of basic principles.
- Comprehend the application of virtual reality in various fields.

2. Application and Analysis:

- Analyze the potential of virtual reality to address real-world problems.
- Apply virtual reality in presenting creative solutions.
- Engage in active and reflective collaboration during problem-solving.

Material: Pc, projector, internet connection.

I. Introduction (15 minutes)

- Explain the basic concepts of virtual reality, such as immersion, virtual environments, and necessary devices.
- Facilitate a brief discussion to ensure students grasp the fundamental principles of virtual reality.

II. Practical examples (30 minutes)

- Showcase brief demos or videos illustrating specific VR application of how virtual reality is used in various fields, such as medicine (surgical simulations), architecture (virtual building tours), education (immersive learning), and entertainment (games and interactive experiences).
- Discuss the potential impact of these applications on society and various industries.
- Allow questions and comments to encourage active student participation.

III. Group discussion (15 minutes)

- Divide students into small groups.
- Brainstorming Solutions. Assign each group a real-world problem or need and ask them to collaborate in identifying how virtual reality could address that situation.
- Facilitate the discussion, encouraging students to consider the advantages and disadvantages of implementing virtual reality in the chosen context.

IV. Presentation of Potential Solutions (25-30 minutes)

- Each group presents their problem identification and proposes potential solutions using virtual reality.
- Encourage questions and comments between groups to promote reflection and collaboration.

V. Reflection and Conclusions (10 minutes)

- Facilitate a general reflection on the lesson and the proposed solutions.
- Conclude by highlighting the potential of virtual reality to address real-world problem, how the demonstrated VR applications might influence their lives or future careers and the importance of collaboration in idea generation.
- Provide additional resources for those interested in exploring virtual reality further.

Assessment:

- Participation and contributions in group discussions.
- Ability to identify problems and propose creative solutions with virtual reality.
- Quality of group presentations: clarity, arguments, resources and defense of the design.

Extension:

- Invite students to research further on virtual reality projects addressing real-world problems.
- Challenge students to develop a more detailed concept for the application of virtual reality in solving a specific problem identified during the lesson or assign a creative writing task where students imagine a day in their life enhanced by virtual reality technology and its applications.

Lesson 2

Getting into VR - 2 sessions

Objectives:

1. Knowledge and Understanding.

- Understand the role of these devices in immersion and their contribution to creating realistic virtual experiences.

2. Application.

- Use virtual reality headsets and controllers in practical exercises to apply the acquired knowledge.

Material: Oculus Quest headset, VR software – Quest 2 First steps

I. Introduction (15 minutes)

- Explain the main components of virtual reality headsets and controllers.
- Discuss how these devices contribute to immersion.
- Provide a brief overview of the technology behind the devices, emphasizing their role in creating a realistic virtual experience.
- Demonstrate how to navigate the metaverse and use the immersive software.

II. Hands-On Practice (70 minutes)

- Offer students the opportunity to use virtual reality headsets and controllers in a practical session.

- Conduct simple exercises to help them become familiar with the interface and functionalities of the devices. First steps tutorials.
- Emphasize the importance of proper usage and handling of the equipment.

III. Group Discussion and Reflection (15 minutes)

- Facilitate a group discussion where students can share their experiences using the virtual reality devices.
- Discuss any challenges encountered and the potential applications of these tools in various fields.
- Reflect on how the use of headsets and controllers enhances the overall virtual reality experience.

Assessment:

- Evaluate students based on their participation in hands-on practice, engagement in the virtual scenario, and their contributions to the group discussion.

Lesson 3

Virtual Reality Methodology with Gravity Sketch - 7//9 Sessions

Objectives:

1. Application.

- Use headsets and controllers in practical exercises to apply acquired knowledge.
- Navigate the lobby, differentiate between Personal and Organization Spaces, and use basic drawing tools in Gravity Sketch.

2. Evaluation.

- Actively participate in group discussions, sharing experiences and reflections on the use of Gravity Sketch in virtual reality design.

3. Creating.

- Design creative solutions for real-world problems using Gravity Sketch.

Material: Oculus Quest headset, VR software – Gravity Sketch

I. Introduction (15 minutes)

- Present the Gravity Sketch application and its basic functions.
- Discuss the significance of Gravity Sketch in the realm of virtual reality design.

II. Training On Virtual Sketch (4-5 sessions)

- Conduct a hands-on tutorial where students learn to use the basic tools of Gravity Sketch to create simple virtual objects.

- Basics to cover:
 - Navigating the main lobby area.
 - The difference between Personal & Org Spaces.
 - Going into a collab room.
 - Moving in space. Scaling in space.
 - Controller layout.
 - Settings tools overview (including suggested basic settings).
 - Drawing tools overview.
- Guide them through the process, emphasizing key features and techniques.

III. Small project (2-3 sessions)

- Students are challenged to use Gravity Sketch to design an object that addresses a specific problem or need, allowing them to apply what they have learned and create a simple object.
- Encourage creativity and experimentation with the tools learned during the tutorials.

IV. Group Discussion and Reflection (35 minutes)

- Allow students to share their creations and tools used within small groups.
- Facilitate a discussion on the challenges faced, interesting discoveries, and potential applications of Gravity Sketch in design.

Assessment

- Evaluate students based on their participation in the tutorials, the creativity demonstrated in their individual projects, and their engagement in the group discussion.

Lesson 4

Project Evaluation and Presentation in Virtual Reality with Gravity Sketch- 2 Sessions

Objectives:

1. Synthesis.

- Articulate their work in front of peers, emphasizing key decisions and effective solutions.

2. Evaluation.

- Argue and defend key decisions during presentations.
- Provide constructive feedback on their peers' work.

Material: Oculus Quest headset, VR software – Gravity Sketch

I. Project Review and Enhancement (15 minutes)

- Students will revisit their virtual reality projects, taking into consideration feedback provided during the previous lesson.
- Emphasize the importance of iterative design and improvement.

II. Project presentation (30 minutes)

- Each group will present their Gravity Sketch project to the class, explaining the solution to the problem and key decisions made.
- Encourage students to use visuals, demonstrations, and articulate explanations during their presentations.

III. Peer assessment (15 minutes)

- Students provide written evaluations for their peers' projects, offering constructive criticism.
- This mirrors the challenge's emphasis on using Gravity Sketch to address specific problems, promoting critical analysis.

IV. Reflection and Goal Setting (10 minutes):

- Students reflect on feedback received, aligning with the iterative design process.
- Goal setting connects to the challenge by encouraging students to apply their learning in future virtual reality projects.

Assessment

- Evaluate students based on the quality of their project revisions and the effectiveness of their presentations.
- Assess the depth and engagement of students' contributions to the group discussion.
- Consider the insights provided in the peer assessments as part of the overall evaluation.

Waves & Snakes

DESIGN & TECHNOLOGY Age 15-16

Learning Aims:

- Understand the process of developing and producing an artistic work by integrating digital tools with analog tools and processes.
- Recognize the importance of documentation and conceptualization before initiating a project.
- Collaboratively explore problems and needs in the development and production of tasks.
- Develop graphic-plastic ideas through drawing, combining analog processes with digital processes (image and digital video editing, drawing in 3D with Gravity Sketch).
- Develop prototypes that respond to the identified needs.
- Collaboratively produce a plastic-sculptural work that intervenes in the space of the educational center.
- Develop strategies that favor creativity and critical thinking to design innovative solutions.
- Develop the ability to establish relationships and synergies between different disciplines, integrating art, science, and technology.
- Understand, through experience, the importance of a comprehensive education that combines the symbolic-humanistic dimension with the scientific-technical one.

Context

It is essential that our students participate in collaborative environments that engage in interdisciplinary projects combining digital and analog tools.

The educational experience presented here emphasizes the integration of scientific-technological and artistic-humanistic fields.

With these premises in mind, a didactic unit was designed within the subject of Artistic Drawing for the First Year of High School, involving 27 students from both science and humanities tracks. The unit centers around the production of a picto-sculptural artistic work that will intervene in a space within the educational center.

Implementation

Students were enabled to understand the phases of conceptualization, documentation, ideation, experimentation, and production in the realization and exhibition of an artistic project.

The experience also allowed the development of skills in collaborative work, critical judgment to respond to specific problems, and sensitivity to the impact and symbolic communication of it.

The experience had a **direct connection with VR**, utilizing the Gravity Sketch application for students to become familiar with this environment and basic concepts of design 3D (vectors, splines, nurbs curves, extrusions...).

A formal presentation of the activity occurred during the mobility (28/03/2023) held in Torrelodones within the Erasmus + project.

Practice

The experience was developed over a quarter addressing three phases:

Phase 1

Conceptualization and two-dimensional graphic representations - 12 Sessions

On the myths and the previous metaphor of the "snake" as a symbol of knowledge and knowledge are worked drawings and graphisms that represent and express opposing ideas (unity/fragmentation, predictability/spontaneity, economy/profusion, etc.). The book "The Syntax of the Image" by Dandis A. and the book "Art and Visual Perception" by R. Arnheim are taken as references.

In two sessions the opposite terms are presented as complementary, meanings and nuances are related and synonyms are proposed.

In one session parallels are drawn between verbal language and graphic language.

In three sessions drawings are made: students make pencil sketches trying to represent these dichotomies graphically, working different levels of iconicity (from abstraction to a naturalistic figuration).

In a session, the ambivalence and complementarity of the positive graphic space and the negative graphic space (figure and background) are presented to the students so that they can apply it in the drawing and final design .

In five sessions the students, from the previous sketches made, have to give definitive form to a personal design that expresses one or several of the dichotomies raised. In all the compositions the following instructions will be taken into account: DIN A4 format in landscape layout, black background, wavy shape lace as the main frame of the design and realization of two versions exchanging positive forms and negative forms (dark and light).

At the end of this phase each student must have made two designs with the established conditions that will then be incorporated, as part of a set, to the design of the final work.

In the animation "Waves and Snakes" (<https://mediateca.educa.madrid.org/video/su6kj8zjq3hoaj4>) you can see the results of these initial works.

Phase 2

Assembly and construction of two three-dimensional collective works that were exhibited in educational center - 12 Sessions

Assembly in a sculptural set of the works made on paper by the students. On two different structures, first a metal cage of 1x1 x1 .8 meters and then in a structure made with pallets on a surface of 5 m², join the works on paper generating warped surfaces simulating serpentine forms that cross the structure, entering and leaving it.

The 54 compositions on cardboard are distributed in small groups. During 3 sessions each group tests different combinations and performs a final modular composition.

Subsequently three sessions are occupied to make the first assembly on the structure of the metal cage joining the different parts (modules) made by groups. Finally, it is decided to make a second assembly more complex on a structure of pallets. In this second assembly more sessions were necessary, up to five, because both the composition and the crimping and assembly systems that had to be devised and tested were more complex.

In the slideshow "Waves and Snakes" (<https://mediateca.educa.madrid.org/video/fw4fq492gkxpu5ts>) you can see photographs of the realization of both montages.

Phase 3

Presentation and VR demonstration within the framework of the Erasmus + project on VR - 8 Sessions

The students of the group were distributed in six working groups in order to prepare an oral presentation supported by a digital graphic document in which they were presented from different areas (physics, biology, mathematics, literature and myths, art and architecture, splines and curves nurbs in computer design, sport) the subject of curves and waves.

There were four sessions of preparation of the groups for the selection of contents, realization of the documentation and preparation of the oral presentations. A group was responsible for the presentation and explanation of the work process of the sculptural installation.

Another group, specifically, trained in four more sessions with the Gravity Sketch program to perform a VR demonstration drawing with splines and nurbs curves warped shapes similar to those made analogically in the installation.

The formal presentation of the installation was made, as well as the exhibitions of the students prepared in this third phase, in one of the work sessions.

Fostering Virtual Reality in Education: Efforts and Achievements

This section unfolds the dedicated efforts of the Erasmus project in incorporating virtual reality technology into the school culture. It succinctly details the initiatives taken by the institution to seamlessly adopt and integrate cutting-edge technologies, providing a glimpse into the transformative journey of educational evolution through virtual reality.

Guidance on Researching Educational Applications

Teachers were trained in researching and selecting educational applications for use in their respective subject areas and classrooms. The training encompassed criteria for application selection, utilization of available resources, and strategies for evaluating the educational impact of each application.

Initial Training for Teachers and Students

During the initial training process for both teachers and students, the emphasis was on practical steps using Oculus Quest. This involved hands-on training in fundamental aspects to ensure proficiency in utilizing virtual reality.

Pilot sessions in Specific Virtual Reality Applications

Pilot sessions were conducted to instruct teachers and students on the practical use of various virtual reality (VR) applications. These hands-on workshops introduced participants to a range of applications, including Beat Saber, Echo VR, Rec Room, Gravity Sketch, Boobot, Piano Vision, Virtual Medecine and Eleven Table Tennis. The focus was on providing an immersive learning experience, allowing participants to explore and familiarize themselves with the functionalities and educational potentials of each application. The outcomes and feedback from these pilot sessions played a crucial role in refining subsequent training strategies and tailoring the use of VR applications in the educational setting.

VR Workshops and Student Engagement

Throughout the course, workshops were held during breaks in collaboration with the guidance department. These sessions provided students with opportunities to use VR headsets and experiment with virtual reality. The workshops garnered significant enthusiasm and engagement from students, showcasing a strong interest in incorporating VR into their learning experiences. The positive reception has been instrumental in shaping ongoing strategies for integrating virtual reality into the educational environment.

Unity Development Course

In the "Introduction to Virtual Reality" seminar, taught by Alejandro Vélez, various aspects of the Unity game engine were addressed. Considering that the training was aimed at teachers who had never or almost never worked with this software, some basic concepts were explained, such as:

- What is Unity?
- Installation and configuration
- Unity interface

- Selecting objects, Navigation and Gizmo of a 3D scene.
- Game Objects, Components, Prefabs and Assets
- Video Game Design
- Development of a VR applications and use of plugins

To finish the training, a sample project was presented with some of the necessary components of any interactive application with Virtual Reality.

VR-Enhanced Lessons and Tutorials

As part of the ongoing efforts to integrate cutting-edge technology into the educational landscape, the center has formulated two distinct unit lessons. One lesson revolves around the technological processes, while the other delves into the artistic subject, demonstrating the seamless fusion of technology and art in the classroom.

Additionally, the center has curated comprehensive tutorials aimed at empowering educators in utilizing Unity and VR technologies. These tutorials provide step-by-step guidance on creating applications tailored for virtual reality, fostering an immersive and interactive learning environment. These initiatives reflect the center's commitment to embracing innovative teaching methodologies and enhancing the educational journey through the incorporation of virtual reality.

Link to tutorials:

<https://mediateca.educa.madrid.org/documentos/hjqajzyzff2dqx>

Conclusions

Knowing the technology, the potential, and the process behind the VR applications, you can now better understand how this technology became one of the most important innovations of our time.

The possibilities of its use in education, and entertainment confirms that the future generations of virtual reality devices can truly change not only the way we are learning but, and the way we live, work, create, and stay connected. Some specialists see immersive technology as the next technological step after smartphones in terms of personal-use devices. It's hard to say when it will happen, but we are not at all far from that.

In this e-book, we have attempted to convey the usefulness of VR as a technology suitable for education and training purposes. This comes from the fact that VR systems allow the student to experience a wide range of scenarios, including those that are physically impossible to set up in the classroom. The range of material that can be taught is vast, ranging from science and mathematics to history, archeology, and cultural Heritage.

We have seen that the experiential nature of VR is compatible with a constructivist view of education which perceives learning as an ongoing and active process and the students are encouraged to explore and experiment to form new ideas and concepts and in order to reformulate old ones.

The potential of virtual reality in education is demonstrated by the interest it has generated in researchers and organizations in this field. Here we have described several examples of using VR in educational contexts to give a taste of the types of applications and subjects covered.

These are inexhaustible with many new applications currently being developed. New systems are also being developed for applied educational purposes, while basic research is being done on the effectiveness of using virtual environments and VR on learning and other cognitive abilities such as memorization, spatial awareness, and perception.

The adoption of Virtual Reality as a valuable tool for transforming education has the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning, enhance student engagement and motivation. The future implications of Virtual Reality (VR) in education are vast and transformative. It promises us enormous opportunities to transform teaching and learning, offering innovative solutions to long-standing challenges and enabling students to reach their full potential.

By harnessing the power of VR technology, educators, policymakers, and stakeholders can create immersive, engaging, and inclusive learning experiences that prepare students for success in the digital age. It's time to embrace virtual reality and unlock the full potential of education for all students.

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